

NK6 transcription factor related, locus 1 (Drosophila) or NK6 homeobox 1 (NKX6-1) : Machine learning discoveries of 2nd order synergy in Meningiomas

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Abstract

Background : NKX6.1 is required for the development of β cells, in pancreas (an organ of the digestive system and endocrine system of vertebrates). β cells are specialized endocrine cells located within the pancreatic islets of Langerhans, which are responsible for the production and release of insulin and amylin. It is implicated in central nervous system, mesenchymal tissues, repair of brain and spinal cord lesions, well-differentiated neuroendocrine tumors, basal-like breast cancer, cervical cancer and colorectal cancer. However, its role in meningiomas has not yet been determined completely. Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 tumors from all 3 World Health Organization (WHO) grades (I through III) using clinical, gene expression, and sequencing data and using unsupervised clustering analysis identified 3 molecular types (A, B, and C) that reliably predicted recurrence. Further, these groups did not directly correlate with the WHO grading system, which classifies more than half of the tumors in the most aggressive molecular type as benign. **Issue** : Increasing evidence point to the fact that meningioma classification and grading, that is based on histopathology does not always accurately predict tumor aggressiveness and recurrence behaviour and knowledge of the underlying biology of the treatment resistant meningiomas and the impact of genetic alterations in these tumors, is lacking. At the current stage more genomic studies are required to unravel the role of other genes and their interactions with other genetic factors. **Resolution** : In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. Adapting this search engine to the Meningioma dataset, i present here 2nd order combinations of NKX6-1, some of which have been known to exist via wet lab experiments, but many are yet to be tested. The reveals combinations might help oncologists/biologists test possible hypotheses that might be the causing factors in meningioma. Further, in my limited grasp, if proven true, the combinations revealed

*ML dicoveries of NKX6-1 synergy in Meningiomas

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by the search engine might pave way for development of gene based therapies aimed at resolving pathological issues related to meningiomas.

Keywords: NKX6-1, Meningioma, Sensitivity analysis, Machine learning.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Meningioma

Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. They arise from the arachnoid cap cells. These arachnoid cap cells are specialized cells that make up the arachnoid mater (one of the three protective membranes covering the brain and spinal cord). The arachnoid mater is one of the three meninges. The other two that constitute the meninges are dura mater and pia mater.

1.1.1. World Health Organization (WHO) classification

The meningiomas are classified into three grades by WHO under the Central Nervous System tumours, namely, Grade I (benign), Grade II (atypical) and Grade III (anaplastic/malignant), based on histopathology or subtype (Louis et al. [3]). As of 2021, there exists 12 histopathological meningioma subtypes according to a mini-review by Torp

et al. [4]. They are meningothelial, fibrous, transitional, psammomatous, angiomatous, microcystic, secretory, lymphoplasmacyte-rich, atypical, chordoid, clear cell and anaplastic (malignant) meningioma.

1.1.2. Historical perspective

Czarnetzki et al. [5] investigated a skull that was excavated at Steinheim/Murr (Baden-Württemberg, Germany) and consisted of a well preserved plagiocephalic cranium, with most of the facial skeleton intact. Their results of stratigraphical dating suggested the fossil specimen of *Homo steinheimensis*, was about 3,65,000 years old. In the fossil, they found that several features of the inner cranial table were consistent with a diagnosis of meningioma.

As documented in Okonkwo and Laws Jr [6], in 1614, Felix Plater, Professor of Medicine, issued a case report from the University of Basel on Caspar Bonecortius, a noble knight stating -

began to lose his mind gradually over a two year period, to such an extent that finally he was completely stupefied and did nothing rationally. He had no desire for food and ate only when forcibly fed. ... Finally after matters had gone on thus for six months, he died.

Further, the autopsy report of Plater stated the following -

a round fleshy tumor, like an acorn. It was hard and full of holes and was as large as a medium-sized apple. It was covered with its own membrane and was entwined with veins. However, it was free of all connections with the matter of the brain, so much so that when it was removed by hand, it left behind a remarkable cavity.

This was the first case in the history that documented a patient with a lesion that was most compatible with a meningioma.

Next, in a contribution by Italian scientists, Paterniti [7] documents the first contribution of Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri in 1813 in a manuscript *Trattato di Chirurgia Pratica*, which was never published. Its discovery was made accidentally by David Giordano, who referred in detail in an article on surgeon of Pisa in *La chirurgia di Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri*. *Riv Storia Sci MedNat*. 1927: XVIII (3-4): 75-106. The unpublished manuscript of 488 pages describes that Vacca Berlinghieri proposed and performed a most bold radical operation. After a craniectomy with five or six burr holes on the outskirts of the fungus, the tumor was removed together the dura mater from which it originated, tying the cut vessels.

In 1847, Zanobi Pecchioli, Professor of Clinical Surgery and Operative Medicine at Modena and then at Siena University, published an account of surgeries performed during 16 years, from 1832 to 1847 (16 of the 1524 reported operations involved trephining of the skull). In one of these interventions, he carried out on July 29 1835, in Siena, for the resection of a meningioma, a defined fungus of the duramater. The case was not referred in the literature by Pecchioli but was described by in Pecchioli [8]. Finally, Cushing [9] coined the modern term of "meningioma".

Figure 1: A schematic diagram of different pathways in different meningiomas, as provided by Szulzewsky et al. [12] under CC-BY Attribution 4.0 International license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

1.1.3. Pathophysiology

Meningiomas arise from arachnoidal cap cells, most of which are near the vicinity of the venous sinuses, and this is the site of greatest prevalence for meningioma formation. The dural venous sinuses (also called dural/cerebral/cranial sinuses) are venous sinuses (channels) found between the periosteal and meningeal layers of dura mater in the brain. They receive blood from the cerebral veins, and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) from the subarachnoid space via arachnoid granulations. They mainly empty into the internal jugular vein. Cranial venous sinuses communicate with veins outside the skull through emissary veins. These communications help to keep the pressure of blood in the sinuses constant. (contributors [10] and Pamir et al. [11]) A schematic diagram for different pathways in different meningiomas has been provided in figure 1.

1.2. NK6 homeobox 1 (NKX6-1)

Nkx6.1, a new member of the NK homeobox gene family, was identified in rodent pancreatic islet beta-cell lines. The pattern of expression suggested that this gene product might control of islet development and/or regulation of insulin biosynthesis. Inoue et al. [13] reported cloning of human NKX6.1, characterization of its genomic structure, and its chromosomal localization. They also determined that NKX6.1 mapped to 4q21.2-q22.

1.3. Roles of NKX6-1 in different disease

Qiu et al. [14] reported the isolation, sequence and developmental expression in the **central nervous system** of several members of the chicken and mouse NKX gene family. These are the earliest genes to be regionally expressed in the neural plate while being expressed just above the axial mesendoderm (prechordal mesendoderm and notochord). They observed that each NKX gene had a distinct spatial pattern of expression along the anterior-posterior axis of the ventral central nervous system, i.e NKX-2.2 was expressed along the entire axis, while NKX-2.1 was restricted to the forebrain, and NKX-6.1 and NKX-6.2 were largely excluded from the forebrain. They were also expressed in distinct patterns along the dorsal-ventral axis. These genes were expressed in both the ventricular and mantle zones, i.e in the mantle zone NKX-6.1 was co-expressed with ISLET-1 in a subset of motor neurons. They found that expression of NKX-6.1 was induced by the axial mesendoderm and by sonic hedgehog protein. BMP-7 repressed NKX-6.1 expression. While the notochord could induce NKX-6.1 expression in the anterior neural plate, sonic hedgehog protein did not, suggesting that the notochord produces additional molecules that could regulate ventral patterning.

Cai et al. [15] identified a specific subpopulation of motor neurons, the median half of the lateral motor neuron column (LMCm), that retained a strong expression of NKX-6.1. Further, they reported novel patterns of NKX-6.1 expression in several **mesenchymal tissues** surrounding Sonic hedgehog (Shh)-expressing cells, including esophageal mesenchyme, ventral spinal meninges, and dorsal tracheal mesenchyme. They observed that while Shh signaling was required for NKX-6.1 expression in the ventral neural tube and spinal meninges, an Shh-independent pathway appeared to operate in regulating NKX-6.1 expression in the foregut. The persistent and robust expression of NKX-6.1 in motor neurons and mesenchymal cells suggested an important role for NKX-6.1 in controlling cell fate specification and differentiation.

The adult central nervous system (CNS) contains different populations of immature cells that might be used to **repair brain and spinal cord lesions**. After isolating Nestin⁺ Sox2⁺ neural multipotential cells from the adult human spinal cord using the neurosphere method (i.e. non adherent conditions and defined medium), Mamaeva et al. [16] reported the isolation and long term propagation of another population of Nestin⁺ cells from this tissue using adherent culture conditions and serum. Further characterization allowed them to identify the NKX6.1 transcription factor as a marker for these cells. They observed that NKX6.1 was expressed in vivo by CNS vascular muscular cells located in the parenchyma and the meninges.

Tseng et al. [17] evaluated the potential use of NKX6-1 as a diagnostic marker for **well-differentiated neuroendocrine tumors** (WDNETs). In total, they analyzed 178 primary and 26 metastatic WDNETs of different origins for NKX6-1, TTF-1, CDX2, ISL1, and polyclonal PAX8. They observed that NKX6-1 was expressed in 36 of the 44 (82%) primary pancreatic WDNETs, 12 of the 18 (67%) primary duodenal WDNETs, and rarely in pulmonary, gastric, and appendiceal WDNETs. The combinatorial use of NKX6-1, CDX2, TTF-1, and ISL1 distinguished WDNETs of different origins with high specificity. Thus, their results indicated that the inclusion of NKX6-1 in an immunohistochemical panel would be beneficial for identifying the primary sites of WDNETs. Li et al. [18] found that expression of NKX6.1 was higher in **basal-like breast**

cancer than in other subtypes. Their in loss-of-function experiments on basal-like breast cancer cell lines, NKX6.1-depleted cells exhibited reduced cell growth. Their results indicated that NKX6.1 directly up-regulated IL6 expression and thus concluded that NKX6.1 was a factor for IL-6-regulated growth and tumor formation in basal-like breast cancer.

Li et al. [18]’s findings indicated that methylation in the promoter regions of WT1, NKX6-1 and DBC1 is correlated with **cervical cancer** tumorigenesis in Uygur women.

Chang et al. [19] investigated whether hypermethylation of NKX6.1 might be a prognostic biomarker for **colorectal cancer** (CRC). They quantitatively examined the NKX6.1 methylation levels in 151 pairs of CRC tissues by using methylation-specific PCR analysis and found that NKX6.1 was hypermethylated in 35 of 151 CRC tissues (23%). Their results demonstrated that methylation of NKX6.1 is a novel prognostic biomarker in CRC and that it may be used as a predictor of the response to chemotherapy.

Many of the different synergies represented as combinations of genes/proteins have been experimentally tested and published. However, there are combinations that have yet to be explored. I address the problem of identifying these unexplored combinations via use of a machine learning based search engine in the next section.

1.4. Insight behind the work

Across all search engines has the fundamental principle remains the same i.e to capture the pattern available in the data and based on that pattern, rank a list of queries. Different algorithms can be applied, however if the fundamental pattern is captured accurately, then the rankings will remain approximately the same, with slight variations, across the different kinds of search engines used. I use one search engine, however, vary the way the patterns are captured via use of different sensitivity methods. Each sensitivity method uses a different flavour/mathematical formulation to compute the sensitivity indices to estimate the influence of the involved factors. These involved factors are genes that play a role in cell biology, in the above research. The insight is that all methods will capture the sensitivity of the involved factors based on their recorded regulations and the search engine will rank the combination of factors based on these sensitivity indices. Since the role of involved factors are captured properly, the search engine will give appropriate rankings to the combinations, thus capturing which gene combinations might be playing significantly in a biological phenomena. The above work shows rankings for experimentally confirmed combinations as well as unexplored/untested combinations. These rankings are not just numbers. They point to the existence of biological synergy in the form of gene combinations, whether tested in wet lab or unexplored till now. Finally, the findings suggest that the rankings are conserved across the different sensitivity methods used.

1.5. Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution

In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. The work uses SVM package by Joachims [20] in <https://www.cs.cornell.edu/>

people/tj/svm_light/svm_rank.html. I use the adaptation to rank 2^{nd} order gene combinations. The sensitivity package by Pujol et al. [21] was used to develop the search engine pipeline. The current research uses the Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion (HSIC) and SOBOL method, implemented in the sensitivity package mentioned above. I use three different kernels under the HSIC method namely, • laplace, • linear and • rbf. For SOBOL method, I use • sobol-2002, and • sobol-jansen. Each of these variants or kernels have been implemented in the sensitivity package and option has been provided in the search engine code to generate the rankings for a particular gene, using a choice of a kernel/variant at a time. Technical details about the variants and kernels can be found in references cited in Pujol et al. [21].

2. Methods

2.1. Static data from Patel et al. [1]

Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 meningioma samples from 140 patients, and according to the WHO histopathological classification system for meningioma, they found 121 tumors were of grade I (benign), 32 were of grade II (atypical), and 7 were of grade III (malignant). To determine whether meningiomas could be differentiated based on gene expression profiles, they used principal component analysis (PCA) on a discovery set of 97 tumors (i.e 77 WHO grade I and 20 WHO grade II). Next, they employed nonnegative matrix factorization (NMF) clustering (a unsupervised machine-learning approach) for $k = 2$ to $k = 7$ using the 1,500 genes that varied most among the tumor samples. They report that after 1,000 iterations, 3 clusters ($k = 3$) emerged as providing the best fit as determined by the consensus membership, cophenetic, and silhouette scores. They evaluated the cluster significance of the 3 subtypes using SigClust (Huang et al. [22]) and observed statistical significance between cluster boundaries, which exhibited significant differences in WHO grade representation.

2.2. Design for static data from Patel et al. [1]

The procedure begins with the listing of all C_k^n combinations for k number of genes from a total of n genes. Here n can be the choice of the biologist. k is ≥ 2 and $\leq (n - 1)$. Each of the combination of order k represent a unique set of interaction between the involved genetic factors. Since the sensitivity analysis methods require a sample for a particular observation, a steep gaussian distribution was generated with a jitter (noise) added to the deviation from the reported point measurement of 0.005. In this experiment, the distribution contained 10 measurements (including the point of measurement under consideration). This is repeated for each point of measurement.

To have an averaged ranking, the experiment was designed to run for 25 iterations. In each iteration, the datasets are combined in a specified format which go as input as per the requirement of a particular sensitivity analysis method. Thus for each p^{th} combination in C_k^n combinations, the dataset is prepared in a required format. Details of formatting the data have not been presented in the article to maintain the fluidity and brevity. Interested readers can find examples of forming the data in the sensitivity

analysis package in R. Sensitivity analysis and its relevance in systems biology have been covered in a recently published article by Sinha [23], which forms the foundation for this work. After the data has been transformed, vectorized programming is employed for density based sensitivity analysis and looping is employed for variance based sensitivity analysis to compute the required sensitivity indices for each of the p combinations.

After the above sensitivity indices have been stored for each of the p^{th} combination, for a chosen sensitivity analysis method, the next step in the design of experiment is conducted. Here, the indices are averaged per combination to have a mean index value. These index values form the discriminative features for a particular combination. For a k^{th} order combination, a vector of k elements or indices forms a feature vector. Thus for C_k^n combinations there will be C_k^n vectors, each containing k elements. Next, SVM_{learn}^{Rank} Joachims [20] is used to generate a model on default value C value of 20. In the current experiment on toy model C value has not been tuned. The training set helps in the generation of the model as the different gene combinations are numbered in order which are used as rank indices. The model is then used to generate score on the observations in the testing set using the $SVM_{classify}^{Rank}$ Joachims [20]. This is followed by sorting of these scores along with the rank indices already assigned to the gene combinations. The end result is a sorted order of the gene combinations based on the ranking score learned by the SVM^{Rank} algorithm.

Note that the following is the order in which the files should be executed in R Team [24], in order, for obtaining the desired results (Note that the code will not be explained here) - • use source("extractMeningiomadata.R") • use source("manuscript-2-2.R") • use source("SVMRank-Results-S-mean.R").

2.3. Translating the pipeline into code of execution in R

The execution begins by some preprocessing of the file containing the information regarding the down regulated genes via `source("extractMeningiomadata.R")`. The library containing the sensitivity analysis methods is then loaded in the interface using the command `library(sensitivity)` (Note - this package can be downloaded for free from <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/sensitivity/index.html>). Next a gaussian distribution for a particular transcript level for a gene is generated to have a sample. This is needed in the computation of sensitivity index for that particular gene. A gene of particular choice is selected (in blue) and the choice of the combination is made (here $k = 2$). Later a kernel is used (here rbf for HSIC method). 25 different indices are generated which help in generating aggregate rank using these 25 indices. The Support vector ranking algorithm is employed to generate the scores for different combinations and these scores are then sorted out. This is done using the command `source("SVMRank - Results - S - mean.R")`. A file is generated that contains the combinations in increasing order of influence. Note that 1 means lowest rank and vice versa, for 2^{nd} order combinations for any gene using a particular density based sensitivity index.

2.4. Regarding biological insight

For the recorded gene expression values, the sensitivity indices are computed. The search engine uses the kernel based density method. The kernel method takes the data, that is in a lower dimensional plane and projects it to a higher dimensional plane, with an idea that in a higher dimensional place, there exists a dot product between the projected data. To simply state, the idea is that in a higher dimensional plane the nonlinearities between the data (in lower dimensional plane) will be captured and the data may be segregated from each other via a hyperplane. So, irrespective of the method used to measure the gene expression values, if the measurements capture biological information (to whatever extent they can), then the kernel method will be able to capture the nonlinearities/synergies, if existing and allow the sensitivity analysis method (here density based method) to estimate the strength of influence of each of the factors. Based on the sensitivity indices of combinations of a particular order, the search engine ranks the combinations. Details of search engine are provided in the published work in Sinha [2].

It is important to note that the search engine will not give insight about the mechanism of synergy between the components of a combination. However, if the synergy exists between components of an unexplored/untested combination, then the sensitivity indices will capture the influence of these components taken together (which form a combination of interest) and will rank the combination appropriately. These rankings provide insight about which combination a biologist/oncologist might want to test in a forest of combinations for a given scenario in a cell (whether normal or pathological).

3. Results & Discussion

3.1. NKX6-1 related synergies

Note - NKX6-1 was found to be upregulated in Type B. Upregulation was defined as Type logFC to be > 1 and $FDR \leq 0.001$, in Patel et al. [1]. Also, sorting of scores by the machine learning algorithm were done in ascending order, i.e - top is lowest in ranking. A total of $392 \cdot 2^{nd}$ order combinations of NKX6-1 were recorded.

3.1.1. NKX6-1 - individual genes

The following genes in combination with NKX6-1 showed high rankings - arachidonate 5-lipoxygenase (ALOX5), CD74 molecule (CD74), amyloid beta precursor protein binding family A member 2 (APBA2), collagen type IX alpha 2 chain (COL9A2), elastin (ELN), PR/SET domain 6 (PRDM6), tetraspanin 32 (TSPAN32), FRY microtubule binding protein (FRY), glypican 4 (GPC4), adenylate cyclase 2 (ADCY2), integrin subunit beta 5 (ITGB5), solute carrier family 23 member 2 (SLC23A2), DNA meiotic recombinase 1 (DMC1), CD40 molecule (CD40), regulating synaptic membrane exocytosis 4 (RIMS4), matrix remodeling associated 5 (MXRA5), platelet derived growth factor receptor like (PDGFRL), epoxide hydrolase 3 (EPHX3), Kazal type serine peptidase inhibitor domain 1 (KAZALD1), EBF transcription factor 3 (EBF3), carboxypeptidase E (CPE), collagen type XII alpha 1 chain (COL12A1), SAM and

SH3 domain containing 1 (SASH1), vanin 1 (VNN1), SPARC related modular calcium binding 2 (SMOC2), growth hormone receptor (GHR), cadherin 6 (CDH6), lysyl oxidase like 3 (LOXL3), immunoglobulin superfamily member 21 (IGSF21), neuropilin 2 (NRP2), chromosome 1 open reading frame 198 (C1orf198), PHD finger protein 19 (PHF19), plexin domain containing 2 (PLXDC2), PDZ and LIM domain 2 (PDLIM2), cysteine rich secretory protein LCCL domain containing 1 (CRISPLD1), C-C motif chemokine receptor 2 (CCR2), basic helix-loop-helix family member e41 (BHLHE41), solute carrier family 12 member 5 (SLC12A5), neuritin 1 (NRN1), FCH and mu domain containing endocytic adaptor 1 (FCHO1), leukocyte immunoglobulin like receptor B2 (LILRB2), solute carrier family 6 member 11 (SLC6A11), Fas apoptotic inhibitory molecule 2 (FAIM2), leucine rich repeats and calponin homology domain containing 1 (LRCH1), alpha kinase 3 (ALPK3), ectonucleotide pyrophosphatase/phosphodiesterase 2 (ENPP2), synaptotagmin like 2 (SYTL2), phospholipase C beta 2 (PLCB2), shroom family member 3 (SHROOM3), fibulin 5 (FBLN5), proline-serine-threonine phosphatase interacting protein 1 (PSTPIP1), insulin like growth factor binding protein 4 (IGFBP4), RNA binding motif single stranded interacting protein 3 (RBMS3), atypical chemokine receptor 2 (ACKR2), family with sequence similarity 198, member A (FAM198A / GASK1A), family with sequence similarity 105 member A (FAM105A / OTULINL), spermatogenesis associated 9 (SPATA9), solute carrier family 2 member 12 (SLC2A12), ADAM metalloproteinase domain 12 (ADAM12), AT-rich interaction domain 5B (ARID5B), serine protease 23 (PRSS23), cysteine rich transmembrane BMP regulator 1 (CRIM1), potassium voltage-gated channel subfamily E regulatory subunit 4 (KCNE4), dimethylarginine dimethylaminohydrolase 1 (DDAH1), matrix metalloproteinase 16 (MMP16), sushi domain containing 3 (SUSD3), meiosis 1 associated protein (MIAP), trichohyalin (TCHH), sialic acid binding Ig like lectin 11 (SIGLEC11), matrix remodeling associated 8 (MXRA8), coiled-coil domain containing 74A (CCDC74A), coagulation factor II thrombin receptor like 2 (F2RL2), EBF transcription factor 1 (EBF1), dishevelled binding antagonist of beta catenin 2 (DACT2), myozenin 3 (MYOZ3), somatomedin B and thrombospondin type 1 domain containing (SBSPON), HtrA serine peptidase 1 (HTRA1), trans-golgi network vesicle protein 23 homolog A (TVP23A), proline rich transmembrane protein 2 (PRRT2), armadillo repeat containing 4 (ARMC4), G protein-coupled receptor 27 (GPR27), mono-ADP ribosylhydrolase 2 (MACROD2), interleukin 17D (IL17D), homeobox B2 (HOXB2), dynein axonemal heavy chain 12 (DNAH12), purinergic receptor P2Y14 (P2RY14), family with sequence similarity 131 member A (FAM131A), calcium binding protein 4 (CABP4), BCL2 family apoptosis regulator BOK (BOK), myozenin 1 (MYOZ1), biglycan (BGN), olfactomedin like 1 (OLFML1), fibronectin leucine rich transmembrane protein 2 (FLRT2), SHC adaptor protein 4 (SHC4), kelch repeat and BTB domain containing 12 (KBTBD12), low density lipoprotein receptor class A domain containing 2 (LDLRAD2), ectonucleoside triphosphate diphosphohydrolase 8 (ENTPD8), sialophorin (SPN), metallothionein 1F (MT1F), ras homolog family member T1 pseudogene 2 (RHOT1P2), transmembrane protein 240 (TMEM240), 3-hydroxyacyl-CoA dehydratase 2 (HACD2), glutathione peroxidase 3 (GPX3), long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 937 (LINC00937) and ITGB2 antisense RNA 1 (ITGB2-AS1).

Using the adaptation of the above mentioned search engine, I tabulate the rankings

of 2nd order combination of NKX6-1 with the above list, that were reported to be upregulated in Patel et al. [1]. Table 1 and 2 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 3 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 1 and 2.

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS NKX6-1									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T NKX6-1									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
ALOX5 - NKX6-1	129	223	277	259	CD74 - NKX6-1	100	320	204	232
APBA2 - NKX6-1	117	289	376	239	COL9A2 - NKX6-1	65	277	369	330
ELN - NKX6-1	315	201	62	215	PRDM6 - NKX6-1	136	331	263	326
TSPAN32 - NKX6-1	4	389	262	254	FRY - NKX6-1	250	229	308	32
GPC4 - NKX6-1	348	360	312	385	ADCY2 - NKX6-1	213	199	220	353
ITGB5 - NKX6-1	3	351	282	251	SLC23A2 - NKX6-1	37	347	374	220
DMC1 - NKX6-1	112	353	255	317	CD40 - NKX6-1	244	293	276	286
RIMS4 - NKX6-1	195	329	306	292	MXRA5 - NKX6-1	218	191	206	384
PDGFRL - NKX6-1	39	358	251	247	EPHX3 - NKX6-1	115	258	261	388
KAZALD1 - NKX6-1	344	267	136	331	EBF3 - NKX6-1	327	308	44	283
CPE - NKX6-1	207	252	156	349	COL12A1 - NKX6-1	312	204	169	362
SASH1 - NKX6-1	131	291	317	270	VNN1 - NKX6-1	42	304	256	273
SMOC2 - NKX6-1	266	202	115	214	GHR - NKX6-1	28	259	298	319
CDH6 - NKX6-1	110	243	301	288	LOXL3 - NKX6-1	166	318	224	337
IGSF21 - NKX6-1	139	309	351	284	NRP2 - NKX6-1	236	366	358	81
C1orf198 - NKX6-1	91	316	340	226	PHF19 - NKX6-1	156	326	285	352
PLXDC2 - NKX6-1	134	290	203	209	PDLIM2 - NKX6-1	97	282	344	296
CRISPLD1 - NKX6-1	106	227	200	323	CCR2 - NKX6-1	135	324	247	275
BHLHE41 - NKX6-1	92	355	313	217	SLC12A5 - NKX6-1	319	97	287	367
NRN1 - NKX6-1	358	214	202	184	FCHO1 - NKX6-1	220	362	207	49
LILRB2 - NKX6-1	75	263	280	282	SLC6A11 - NKX6-1	204	234	160	339
FAIM2 - NKX6-1	242	235	217	297	LRCH1 - NKX6-1	82	272	341	211
ALPK3 - NKX6-1	86	383	303	210	ENPP2 - NKX6-1	101	385	223	202
SYTL2 - NKX6-1	230	247	267	15	PLCB2 - NKX6-1	89	245	304	218
SHROOM3 - NKX6-1	307	153	213	378	FBLN5 - NKX6-1	61	233	368	285
PSTPIP1 - NKX6-1	48	343	270	374	IGFBP4 - NKX6-1	38	357	385	222
RBMS3 - NKX6-1	8	339	332	263	ACKR2 - NKX6-1	40	268	233	358

Table 1: 2nd order interaction ranking between NKX6-1 VS Individual members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 1 and 2 graphically, with the following influences - ● Individual members w.r.t NKX6-1 with NKX6-1 – > ALOX5 / CD74 / APBA2 / COL9A2 / ELN / PRDM6 / TSPAN32 / FRY / GPC4 / ADCY2 / ITGB5 / SLC23A2 / DMC1 / CD40 / RIMS4 / MXRA5 / PDGFRL / EPHX3 / KAZALD1 / EBF3 / CPE / COL12A1 / SASH1 / VNN1 / SMOC2 / GHR / CDH6 / LOXL3 / IGSF21 / NRP2 / C1orf198 / PHF19 / PLXDC2 / PDLIM2 / CRISPLD1 / CCR2 / BHLHE41 / SLC12A5 / NRN1 / FCHO1 / LILRB2 / SLC6A11 / FAIM2 / LRCH1 / ALPK3 / ENPP2 / SYTL2 / PLCB2 / SHROOM3 / FBLN5 / PSTPIP1 / IGFBP4 / RBMS3 / ACKR2 / FAM198A / FAM105A / SPATA9 / SLC2A12 / ADAM12 / ARID5B / PRSS23 / CRIM1 / KCNE4 / DDAH1 / MMP16 / SUSD3 / M1AP / TCHH / SIGLEC11 / MXRA8 / CCDC74A / F2RL2 / EBF1 / DACT2 / MYOZ3 / SBSPON / HTRA1 / TVP23A / PRRT2 / ARMC4 / GPR27 / MACROD2 / IL17D / HOXB2 / DNAH12 / P2RY14 / FAM131A / CABP4 / BOK / MYOZ1 / BGN / OLFML1 / FLRT2 / SHC4 / KBTBD12 / LDLRAD2 / ENTPD8 / SPN / MT1F / RHOT1P2 / TMEM240 / HACD2 / GPX3 / LINC00937 / ITGB2-AS1.

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS NKX6-1									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T NKX6-1									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
FAM198A - NKX6-1	172	368	363	307	FAM105A - NKX6-1	22	325	228	324
SPATA9 - NKX6-1	316	238	69	208	SLC2A12 - NKX6-1	164	336	328	290
ADAM12 - NKX6-1	27	312	310	311	ARID5B - NKX6-1	245	370	235	276
PRSS23 - NKX6-1	59	239	221	359	CRIM1 - NKX6-1	187	250	359	298
KCNE4 - NKX6-1	278	281	300	396	DDAH1 - NKX6-1	12	322	286	227
MMP16 - NKX6-1	297	254	130	315	SUSD3 - NKX6-1	6	271	334	255
M1AP - NKX6-1	51	284	373	243	TCHH - NKX6-1	49	305	367	200
SIGLEC11 - NKX6-1	69	387	370	201	MXRA8 - NKX6-1	209	341	360	40
CCDC74A - NKX6-1	216	195	259	261	F2RL2 - NKX6-1	57	317	258	322
EBF1 - NKX6-1	221	226	331	28	DACT2 - NKX6-1	31	211	320	335
MYOZ3 - NKX6-1	111	307	229	207	SBSPON - NKX6-1	56	222	316	204
HTRA1 - NKX6-1	321	64	201	291	TVP23A - NKX6-1	377	31	293	308
PRRT2 - NKX6-1	288	248	205	392	ARMC4 - NKX6-1	308	225	227	14
GPR27 - NKX6-1	326	280	230	391	MACROD2 - NKX6-1	360	41	260	277
IL17D - NKX6-1	302	249	82	334	HOXB2 - NKX6-1	314	210	222	253
DNAH12 - NKX6-1	256	256	240	48	P2RY14 - NKX6-1	224	221	356	361
FAM131A - NKX6-1	286	113	234	262	CABP4 - NKX6-1	253	107	315	346
BOK - NKX6-1	225	158	330	343	MYOZ1 - NKX6-1	165	219	348	348
BGN - NKX6-1	363	288	96	300	OLFML1 - NKX6-1	108	330	379	287
FLRT2 - NKX6-1	228	185	245	375	SHC4 - NKX6-1	206	260	343	332
KBTBD12 - NKX6-1	285	120	327	364	LDLRAD2 - NKX6-1	121	217	236	249
ENTPD8 - NKX6-1	234	237	299	370	SPN - NKX6-1	333	123	239	329
MT1F - NKX6-1	252	103	345	314	RHOT1P2 - NKX6-1	265	372	378	141
TMEM240 - NKX6-1	280	242	264	386	HACD2 - NKX6-1	260	29	253	231
GPX3 - NKX6-1	211	379	318	176	LINC00937 - NKX6-1	238	114	218	242
ITGB2-AS1 - NKX6-1	232	266	274	328					

Table 2: 2nd order interaction ranking between NKX6-1 VS Individual members.

4. Conclusion

Presented here are a range of multiple synergistic NKX6-1 2nd order combinations that were ranked via a machine learning based search engine. Via majority voting across the ranking methods, it was possible to find plausible unexplored synergistic combinations of NKX6-1-X that might be prevalent in meningioma.

Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Author's contributions

Concept, design, in silico implementation - SS. Analysis and interpretation of results - SS. Manuscript writing - SS. Manuscript revision - SS. Approval of manuscript - SS

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

Individual members w.r.t NKX6-1

ALOX5 / CD74 / APBA2 / COL9A2 / ELN / ...
PRDM6 / TSPAN32 / FRY / GPC4 / ADCY2 / ...
ITGB5 / SLC23A2 / DMC1 / CD40 / RIMS4 / ...
MXRA5 / PDGFRL / EPHX3 / KAZALD1 / ...
EBF3 / CPE / COL12A1 / SASH1 / VNN1 / ...
SMOC2 / GHR / CDH6 / LOXL3 / IGSF21 / ...
NRP2 / C1orf198 / PHF19 / PLXDC2 / ...
PDLIM2 / CRISPLD1 / CCR2 / BHLHE41 / ...
SLC12A5 / NRN1 / FCHO1 / LILRB2 / ...
SLC6A11 / FAIM2 / LRCH1 / ALPK3 / ...
ENPP2 / SYTL2 / PLCB2 / SHROOM3 / ...
FBLN5 / PSTPIP1 / IGFBP4 / RBMS3 / ...
ACKR2 / FAM198A / FAM105A / SPATA9 / ...
SLC2A12 / ADAM12 / ARID5B / PRSS23 / ...
CRIM1 / KCNE4 / DDAH1 / MMP16 / SUSD3 / ...
M1AP / TCHH / SIGLEC11 / MXRA8 / CCDC74A / ...
F2RL2 / EBF1 / DACT2 / MYOZ3 / SBSPON / ...
HTRA1 / TVP23A / PRRT2 / ARMC4 / GPR27 / ...
MACROD2 / IL17D / HOXB2 / DNAH12 / P2RY14 / ...
FAM131A / CABP4 / BOK / MYOZ1 / BGN / OLFML1 / ...
FLRT2 / SHC4 / KBTBD12 / LDLRAD2 / ENTPD8 / ...
SPN / MT1F / RHOT1P2 / TMEM240 / HACD2 / GPX3 / ...
LINC00937 / ITGB2-AS1 / NKX6-1

Table 3: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between NKX6-1 and Individual members.

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Source of Data

Data used in this research work was released in a publication in Patel et al. [1]. Permission to use, granted by PNAS.

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